

Some Terpyridyl Complexes of Organotin Chlorides

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Three 2:1 complexes of butyltin trichloride, phenyltin trichloride and diphenyltin dichloride with 2,2',6',2"-terpyridyl have been isolated and characterised. The molar conductance and the infrared data in the region 4000-250 cm⁻¹ support ionic structure of the complexes.

2,2',6',2"-TERPYRIDYL, a terdentate amine has recently attracted attention of various workers as Lewis base. Synthesis and structure of molecular adducts of the ligand with transition^{1,2}, non-transition^{3,4,5}, rare earths^{6,7}, and organometallic acceptors^{4,5,8-10} have been reported. Fergusson *et al.*⁴ isolated terpyridyl complexes of germanium and tin tetrahalides and those of a few organotin chlorides. Mössbauer spectra of some of these compounds was later examined by Debye *et al.*⁵. The X-ray structures of $[(CH_3)_2SnCl_2]_2$, terpyridyl and $(CH_3)_2Sn(NCS)_2$, terpyridyl have been reported^{8,9} and the former being ionic in character containing $[(CH_3)_2SnCl\ terpy]^+$ as a cation and $[(CH_3)_2SnCl_3]^-$ as an anion, while the latter is reported to be a neutral hepta co-ordinated complex with a pentagonal bipyramidal configuration in which the three nitrogens of terpyridyl and two of the thiocyanate groups occupy positions in the pentagonal plane whereas the methyl groups are in the axial position with C-Sn-C angle of 173.7°. A similar structure for neutral terpyridyl complexes of dimethyl-, di-*n*-butyl- and diphenyltin diisothiocyanate has been concluded by May and Curran¹⁰, on the basis of Mössbauer and IR studies. Since infrared studies on terpyridyl complexes of organotin halides have not been so far reported, we considered it worthwhile to synthesise some complexes of organotin chlorides and determine their structure on the basis of such measurements.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by the direct interaction of organotin chlorides with terpyridyl in petroleum ether.

The molecular weights of the complexes were determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene using Beckmann thermometer of accuracy 0.01°. Molar conductance of a 10⁻³M solution was measured in the same solvent by Phillips, magic eye, conductivity bridge model PR 9500 using a dip type conductivity cell. The infrared spectra in nujol were recorded in the range 4000-250 cm⁻¹ using Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer at the Otto Maass Chemical Laboratories, McGill University, Montreal, Canada.

Materials

The organotin chlorides, used in this investigation were obtained from Alpha Inorganics and 2,2',6',2"-terpyridyl from Aldrich Chemicals. They were used without further purification.

Preparation of the complexes

In a representative experiment, to a solution of 2m mole of diphenyltin dichloride in 15 ml of petroleum ether (60°-80°) was added an excess of the ligand in the same solvent with constant stirring.

The precipitated solid was washed several times with the same solvent, dried in vacuum and analysed. The experimental data are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of adduct indicate 2:1 (metal: ligand) stoichiometry. The variation of molar ratio and the order in which the reactants are mixed do not produce a change in the composition of the adducts. The interaction of $BuSnCl_3$ with terpyridyl was studied by Fergusson *et al.*⁴ and a product of m.p. 223° *d* was obtained which analysed correctly to a combining ratio 3:2 ($BuSnCl_3$: Terpy). We fail to confirm this stoichiometry and instead report the product to be $[Terpy.BuSnCl_2]^+ BuSnCl_4^-$, possessing a molar ratio 2:1. Further the m.p. of the 2:1 complex of diphenyltin dichloride with terpyridyl is observed to be 159° and not 104° as reported by the above workers⁴.

The complexes are crystalline solids soluble in chloroform, acetone and nitrobenzene. They are thermally stable and unaffected by atmospheric moisture. The data on the molar conductance and molecular weight listed in Table 1 indicate that the complexes are 1:1 electrolytes.

Infrared spectra

As absorption frequencies of diagnostic value in the infrared spectra of the complexes lie below 1600 cm⁻¹, the absorptions in the region 1600-250 cm⁻¹ are collected in Table 2. The important

TABLE 1. EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR ORGANOTIN TERPYRIDYL COMPLEXES

Complex	m.p. (°C)	Mol. Wt.	Analysis %			Found (Calcd.)	Molar conductance at 35° in nitrobenzene (mho cm ² /mole)
			C	H	N	Sn	
[Terpy.BuSnCl ₂] ⁺ BuSnCl ₄ ⁻	224 d (223 d)	457 (798)	34.61 (34.58)	3.72 (3.63)	5.23 (5.26)	30.10 (29.83)	24.3
[Terpy.PhSnCl ₂] ⁺ PhSnCl ₄ ⁻	> 300	510 (838)	38.43 (38.67)	2.61 (2.51)	4.99 (5.01)	28.22 (28.41)	31.6
[Terpy.Ph ₂ SnCl] ⁺ Ph ₂ SnCl ₃ ⁻	159 (104)	664 (921)	50.56 (50.81)	3.43 (3.37)	4.48 (4.56)	25.74 (25.84)	16.1

TABLE 2. INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF TERPYRIDYL AND ITS ADDUCTS WITH ORGANOTIN CHLORIDES

Assignment	Terpy.	2BuSnCl ₂ .Terpy	2PhSnCl ₂ .Terpy	2Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .Terpy
terpyridyl band ν (C=C and C=N)	1580 vs	1598 vs	1595 vs	1592 s
	1560 vs	1575 vs	1575 s	1570 s
	1470 vs	1482 vs	1480 s	1480 s
	1450 vs	1455 vs	—	—
	1435 vs	1440 vs	1430 s	1430 s
	1420 sh	1405 w	1403 vw	—
ring vibration and ortho substituted pyridine vibration.	1280 w	1320 vs	1320 s	1315 s
	1262 s	1265 m	1300 w	—
	—	1255 m	1250 m	1245 m,br
	—	1197 s	1190 m	1195 w
ring vibration and C-H deformation	1150 m	1167 s	1163 s	1163 m
	1103 s	1138 s	1134 m	—
	1092 m	1097 m	1083 w	1094 w
	1075 s	1072 vw	—	—
	1060 m	1055 w	1053 m	1060 w
	1035 vs	1035 m	1035 m	—
pyridine ring breathing	989 vs	1023 vs	1025 vs	1020 vs
three adjacent ring hydrogens	893 m	873 w	880 w	—
	831 vs	822 m	820 m	—
two groups of four adjacent ring hydrogens	798 w	—	—	—
	765 vs	773 vs	775 vs	775 vs
ligand ring type vibrations	655 vs	655 vs	655 vs	650 w
	625 m	642 m	—	640 w
	510 m	—	505 w	508 w
	420 m	442 s	440 s	440 sh
	406 s	410 s	415 m	415 w
ν (Sn-N)	398 sh	330 vs	330 s	—
ν (Sn-R)	—	605 w	295 vs	295 s
	—	508 m	—	—

s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, v = very, sh = shoulder, br = broad.

changes in the absorptions may be summarised as follows :

- (i) The bands at 1580, 1560, and 1470 cm⁻¹ attributed to C = C, C = N and ring stretchings in the free base are shifted to higher frequency side⁶.
- (ii) A new ring vibration of strong intensity appears at 1320 cm⁻¹.
- (iii) The ligand absorptions at 625 and 420 cm⁻¹ are shifted towards higher frequency side.
- (iv) The doublet at 406 and 398 cm⁻¹ in the uncoordinated base appears as a single absorption.

The above changes indicate the presence of coordinated base and since the pyridine breathing mode at 989 cm⁻¹ is shifted to 1023 ± 3 cm⁻¹ leaving no residual peak at the initial position, it is suggested that all the three nitrogen atoms of ligand are involved in coordination. ν (Sn-N) and ν (Sn-R) have been identified in the far infrared region of the spectra; while ν (Sn-Cl) in the complexes is expected to lie beyond the recorded range^{11,12}. The spectra of all the three complexes closely resemble each other indicating similarity in structure.

On the basis of analytical data agreeing with 2 : 1 (metal : ligand) combining ratio, molecular weight indicating absence of polymeric character,

molar conductance showing the presence of 1 : 1 electrolyte and IR data giving evidence for the co-ordinated base being bonded through all the three nitrogen atoms, the ionic structures suggested for the complexes in Table 1 appear reasonable.

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